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DOSAGE ADJUSTMENTS OF LEVOTHYROXINE IN PATIENTS WITH HYPOTHYROIDISM AND HYPOTHYROIDISM COMPLICATING CORONARY ARTERY DISEASE

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ABSTRACT

BACK GROUND: Hypothyroidism (underactive thyroid) is a condition in which thyroid gland doesn't produce enough of thyroid hormone. Women, are more likely to have hypothyroidism, as it is chronic illness, lifelong therapy with levothyroxine is necessary. The dose should be individualized in the hypothyroidism patients on the basis of clinical response and biochemical tests. Regular monitoring of TSH and thyroxine is recommended when starting therapy or changing the dose. **AIM AND OBJECTIVES:** (i) To evaluate the dosage adjustment of levothyroxine in patients with hypothyroidism and with coronary artery disease. (ii) To assess the serum TSH, serum T3 and serum T4 levels in patients with hypothyroidism. (iii) To monitor the levothyroxine therapy related side effects and dosage adjustments. (iv) To improve patients quality of life. **METHODS:** The study was conducted in Government General Hospital, Guntur, a tertiary care teaching hospital. The sources of data will include the relevant data cards of the patient along with direct observation of the patient. Family history of the patient and risk factors if any are also included. Dose adjustments was done to the subjects included in the study and management parameters are collected. **RESULTS:** We reviewed the following therapeutic categories in the total of 100 subjects 3% of subjects are at the risk of developing coronary artery disease and dosage adjustment was done in 72 subjects and remaining 28 subject's does not require the adjustment. 15% were under replaced and 5% were over replaced. **CONCLUSION:** We concluded that levothyroxine should remain the standard of care for treating hypothyroidism. Thyroid hormone therapy should be initiated as an initial full replacement or as partial replacement with gradual increments in the dose titrated upward using serum thyrotropin as the goal. Dose adjustments should be made with thyrotropin assessment 4–6 weeks after any dosage change. Additional research is also needed to develop thyroid hormone analogs with a favorable benefit to risk profile.

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INTRODUCTION

Hypothyroidism is the most common thyroid disorder, affects women more frequently, and incidence increases with age^{1,2}. 3% of the population is taking long term thyroid replacement therapy, and every year about 4.1 women and 0.6 men per 1000 of the adult population develop hypothyroidism³. Its clinical presentation ranges from asymptomatic to severe, with myxedema coma as a severe complication^{1,2}. Measurement of serum thyroid stimulating hormone is the cornerstone of monitoring levothyroxine replacement, the exception being people with pituitary disease. Cross sectional surveys of patients taking levothyroxine have, however, shown that between 40% and 48% are either over-treated or under-treated. In patients receiving treatment with LT4, dosing changes should be made every 6-8 weeks until the patient's TSH is in target range. The adequacy of thyroid hormone replacement was determined from the current serum

DOSE ADJUSTMENT OF LEVOTHYROXINE

TSH as follows: (i) adequate replacement (normal TSH; 0.4–4.0 mU/l); (ii) over replacement (low TSH; <0.4 mU/l); and (iii) under replacement (high TSH; >4.0 mU/l). If persistent fatigue, somnolence, or subtle cognitive problems (forgetfulness, befuddlement) exist then it is reasonable to increase the dose by 25 µg daily, or on alternate days. Dose Adjustments is required when initiating this drug in elderly patients, patients with coronary heart disease, and in patients with severe or long-existing hypothyroidism. In these patients an initial low dose is recommended, which should be increased slowly and using longer intervals. Patient non-compliance with levothyroxine therapy can sometimes be a problem. When levothyroxine is taken only on the day of attendance for the blood test this typically results in a chronically raised thyroid stimulating hormone level but normal or raised free thyroxine levels, so it is necessary to ask the patient to take the tablets regularly, even if they do not feel different on days when the dose is missed. In most people it is safe to recommend that they take a double dose on the day after a missed tablet (exceptions being active ischemic heart disease and atrial fibrillation)^{1,2}.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

AIM:

To evaluate the dosage adjustment of levothyroxine in patients with hypothyroidism and with coronary artery disease.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To assess the serum TSH, serum T3 and serum T4 levels in patients with hypothyroidism.
2. To monitor the levothyroxine therapy related side effects and dosage adjustments.
3. To improve patients quality of life.

METHODOLOGY:

STUDY DESIGN:

Prospective Observational Study.

STUDY DURATION:

The study is proposed to be conducted in the following 6 months period i.e., from January to June 2016.

STUDY METHOD:

The study was conducted in Government General Hospital, Guntur, a 1200 bedded tertiary care teaching hospital. The sources of data will include the relevant data cards of the patient along with direct observation of the patient. Family history of the patient and risk factors if any are also included.

SAMPLE SIZE:

Maximum possible cases are going to be collected during our study period.

MATERIALS USED:

- Patient consent form
- Patient data collection form
- Therapeutic intervention form
- ADR reporting form
- QOL questionnaire

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Patients with hypothyroidism of either sex.
- Patients with age group 12-70 years.
- Coronary artery disease patients with hypothyroidism and other co-morbidities.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Hyperthyroidism patient
- Hypothyroidism in pregnancy

RESULTS

SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC PARAMETERS:

Figure 1: Gender wise distribution among the study population.

On the basis of gender wise distribution Females (93%) are more prone to hypothyroidism compared to Males (7%) in study population of hypothyroidism (100%).

AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION

FIGURE 2: Age wise distribution among the study population.

On the basis of age wise distribution, hypothyroid patients are more in the age group ranging between 45-55 years and this is less in the age group between 78-88 years.

SUBJECTS AT RISK OF DEVELOPING CORONARY ARTERY DISEASE

Figure 3: Subjects at risk of developing coronary artery disease.

- A – Total number of study population (n= 100)**
- B – subjects at greater risk of developing coronary artery disease**

From the above graph, out of 100 study population 3 subjects were at greater risk of developing coronary artery disease

HYPOTHYROIDISM WITH CO- MORBIDITIES

Figure 4: Hypothyroidism with co-morbidities.

A total of 100 patients were studied to identify the prevalence of the hypothyroidism with other disease conditions. According to their conditions with hypothyroidism they are divided as general hypothyroidism were (65%), hypothyroidism with diabetes were (11%), hypothyroidism With hypertension were (4%), hypothyroidism with diabetes and hypertension were (9%), hypothyroidism with coronary artery disease were (6%) and hypothyroidism with other co-morbidities were (5%).

DOSE ADJUSTMENTS OF LEVOTHYROXINE

Figure 5: Dose adjustments of Levothyroxine.

Of total 100 study population dose adjustment was required in 72 patients and not required in 28 patients.

QOL SCORE IN STUDY POPULATION

Figure 6: QOL score in study population.

QOL scoring was given before (b) and after (a) the treatment, out of 100 study population patients with score <3 (low probability of thyroid dysfunction) were 11 (b), 70(a); score 3-8 (moderate probability of thyroid dysfunction) were 63 (b), 29(a) and score > 9 (high probability of thyroid dysfunction) were 25 (b), 2 (a).

Paired t test for TSH levels:**Table 1: Paired t test for TSH levels.**

	BASE LINE	AFTER 6 WEEKS
MEAN	24.34	15.69
STANDARD DEVIATION (SD)	33.36	25.55
STANDARD ERROR OF MEAN (SEM)	3.33	2.55
P-VALUE		<0.0001

The two-tailed P value is 0.0408, is considered significant. The following parameters were considered at bases line (b) and after 6 months (a). mean value is 24.34 (b) and decreased to 15.69 (a). The SD is 33.36 (b), reduced to 25.55 (a). SEM is 3.33 (b) and has come to 2.55 (a).

Paired t test for T4 levels.**Table 2: Paired t test for T4 levels.**

	BASE LINE	AFTER 6 WEEKS
MEAN	8.896	6.589
STANDARD DEVIATION (SD)	7.37	7.14
STANDARD EEROR OF MEAN (SEM)	0.737	0.714
P-VALUE		<0.0001

The two tailed P-value is 0.0258, is considered significant The following parameters were considered at bases line (b) and after 6 months (a). mean value is 8.896 (b) and decreased to 6.589 (a). The SD is 7.37 (b), reduced to 7.14 (a). SEM is 0.737 (b) and has come to 0.714 (a)

DISCUSSION:

Hypothyroidism is the most common thyroid disorder, affects women more frequently, and incidence increases with age. 3% of the population is taking long term thyroid replacement therapy, and every year about 4.1 women and 0.6 men per 1000 of the adult population develop hypothyroidism. As the long term therapy with levothyroxine is needed in patients, dose adjustment is periodically necessary. Previous studies showed that a weekly dose of LT4 was safe, but levels of TSH takes 6-8 weeks to reach the target range, by considering this daily doses should be recommendable. Since TSH stabilizes earlier in most patients than has been assumed, it is possible to adjust LT4 replacement doses at shorter intervals and thus reduce the time required to obtain optimum replacement.

This prospective study of 100 patients shows that dose adjustment is required for 72 subjects and not required for 28 subjects and patients who completed the study were metabolically stable with no acute illness. Weight gain is a chief complaint of patients with hypothyroidism thus, Body Mass Index (BMI) was included as one of the parameters of our study. Therefore we concluded that TSH levels were not a determinant of future weight changes, and BMI was not a determinant for TSH changes, but an association between weight change and TSH change was present, similar findings were found in the study Lena Bjergved et al., (2014)⁴. We also stated that out of 100 patients, 3 subjects were at high risk of developing coronary artery disease due to long term levothyroxine therapy without adjusting the dose, similar findings were found in the study Christian Selmer et al., (2012)³. In these patients and elderly an initial low dose (12.5 mcg) is recommended, which should be increased slowly. Long term levothyroxine therapy also leads to over (low TSH; <0.4 mU/l) and under (high TSH; >4.0 mU/l) replacement in the patients. During our study 15 subjects were under replaced and 5 subjects were over replaced. 4 %of ADRs were analyzed and reported in our study.

All the study population (n=100) completely filled the questionnaire and selected for analysis. Out of 21 questions a score of <3 was considered as low probability of thyroid dysfunction; 3-8 score was considered as moderate probability of thyroid dysfunction and score of ≥ 9 was considered as high probability of thyroid dysfunction. The answer yes was scored 1 and answer no was scored 0. Out of total respondents 11 were scored <3; 63 were scored 3-8; 25 were scored ≥9 before adjustment and after adjusting the dose 70 were <3; 29 were 3-8 and 2 were ≥9. The obtained results showed that the quality of life of patients was improved after the adjustment when compared before adjustment of levothyroxine, similar results were observed in the study John P. Walsh et al., (2003)⁵.

CONCLUSION

Hypothyroidism is a condition where patients requires long term therapy of levothyroxine and life-long management. Adjusting the dose of levothyroxine periodically (6-8 weeks) based on TSH levels prevents the patients from developing over replacement or under replacement of TSH and can also reduce the risk of developing coronary artery disease. Evaluating the symptoms by scoring gives an understanding about the patient's quality of life before and after the adjustment. Analyzing and reporting the ADRs by observing the lab parameters and physical state of the patients reduces the risk of further complications due to levothyroxine therapy. Patients counselling played an important role in increasing the patient compliance towards the therapy. Patients were also explained about future hazards if dose is not adjusted and worsening of the condition if he/she stops the medication. Dosage adjustment is done by the physician by comparing minimum of 2 lab parameters of the T4 and TSH levels. Along with the physicians, nurses and other medical staff, clinical pharmacist play a crucial role in improving the patient quality of life in hypothyroid patients and evaluating the risk benefit ratio of levothyroxine for better patient care.

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